

Recommended citation: Gomez Puente, S. M., & Wiel, M. v. d. (2021). Competence development through online self-assessment. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 886-896). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14650308.

COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT THROUGH ONLINE SELF-ASSESSMENT

S.M. Gomez Puente¹

Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e)
Eindhoven, the Netherlands

M. van de Wiel

Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e)
Eindhoven, the Netherlands

Conference Key Areas: Lab courses and projects blended and online, Essential elements for the online learning success, Open and online education.

Keywords: *Blended-learning, online self-assessment, self-directed learning, feedback, competency development*

ABSTRACT

Self-regulation and self-assessment are essential skills in the development of competences in engineering education in general, and more specifically, to educate future generations of industrial designers. We created an online *Competence Development Tool*, a competence chart, and implemented this tool in the blended-learning course *Exploratory Sketching*, an elective course for Industrial Design (ID) students at the Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e). The purpose of the *Competence Development Tool* was to encourage students' sketching skills development by setting personal learning goals and regularly self-assessing the progress. An experiment was conducted in two phases with two students' cohorts. This experiment shows the importance of providing online feedback to make students' development insightful and to support self-directed learning in engineering education.

1 INTRODUCTION

The integration of technology in education has become a common practice in higher education to increase students' learning. Research on online and blended-alike methods has shown interesting insights on effectiveness in learning, in students' achievement, to activate students during lectures [1], to facilitate students' assessment [2], and to foster collaborative knowledge construction [3]. Likewise, self-assessment supported by online methods has been proved to be suitable to encourage students to take more responsibility for the learning process. There are, however, less evidences regarding students' course performance (2011) [4].

¹ Corresponding author: Sonia M. Gómez Puente, s.m.gomez.puente@tue.nl

In this study, we explore how an online *Competence Development Tool* (CDT) chart can influence students' attitudes to self-assess regularly own competencies to enhance learning and boost self-directed learning in engineers. We conducted a number of experiments with the use of the CDT with students. During the first experiment, the *Competence Development Tool* was tested with N=52 first year students to analyse behavioural patterns in competence development along 8 weeks. This experiment was repeated three times with subsequent cohorts in different quartiles. The number of students participating in the consecutive three studies consisted of N=46, N=50 and N=43 respectively. Results indicate a positive effect on reflection that support self-assessment. In addition, a study on the relation between attendance and grades indicated that students attending the lessons regularly influences study results. However, when reviewing the students' grades or course achievement no impact is observed. Moreover, the responsible teacher for the course was positive about the developments of students and used the tool to monitor progress and distribute personal feedback effectively over the student population.

2 THEORETICAL INSIGHTS

Research on digital education collects relevant findings about the integration of tools combined with online or blended methods in education. In these studies, it is described how the combination of, for instance, online platforms with peer assessment is used successfully to learn skills [2]. Other studies report about positive effects of flexibilization of education, specifically on the increased students' motivation, on in-depth understanding and critical thinking supported by technology-driven assessment [5]. The use of technology in classroom facilitates not only the transfer of responsibility but also encourages a critical attitude in students to assess own progress and process. Additional benefits of organizing assessment with the help of technology lies in that assessment can be carried out any time in any place while the teacher can still follow students' progress and performance and provide feedback.

Literature reports about interesting insights in learning with the use of self-assessment through online methods. These studies point out the importance of the shift in the teacher's role and indicate positive values in the transfer of responsibility from the teacher to the students towards learning and developing competencies [8]. Assessment for learning increases students' involvement and responsibility in own progress, so that they can re-orient and adjust learning and learning habits influencing the thinking process as well [6-7]. Hattie and Timperley (2007) [8-9] describe the benefits of formative feedback as part of assessment for learning and reflect upon the importance of focusing on task, process and on the self as key elements in learning. 'Just-in-time' feedback becomes essential in this regard to continuously evaluate progress and encourage students' self-regulation. As a 'safe control' mechanism, it helps adjust learning habits potentially influencing course achievements [10], although the success of self-assessment lies in the quality of feedback provided to the student [11].

In learning students to assess own progress critically the notion of self-regulated learning is central [12]. Self-regulated learning implies a reflection on actions which includes metacognitive knowledge, regulation of cognition and motivation by

understanding the knowledge and skills to be acquired with the purpose of adjusting study behavior, learning strategies, goals and activities [12]. In this process, the feedback from the teacher (environmental stimuli) is crucial to help students cope and adjust own learning strategies.

Following the rationale to educate new generations of engineers, the need to promote self-directed learning through encouraging students to critically assess themselves' competencies and learning progress becomes essential. We believe that online systems well supported by feedback can stimulate students' self-evaluation inferring in self-regulation.

3 RATIONALE FOR INNOVATION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Within the Industrial Design program students develop a broad set of competencies and learn how and when to combine them effectively. To successfully develop their competencies it is important that students are aware of all sub-competencies involved, understand when to apply them during the learning process and eventually within the creative process.

The rationale for self-assessment and reflection in this course has a two-fold goal: on the one hand, students are encouraged to critically think on their development by using the criteria on quality of sketching; on the other hand, they reflect upon achievements and adjust progress in a self-directed manner. Another important aspect of this rationale is the experimentation with blended and online forms of education. In addition, the purpose was to get an insight on whether the tools are sufficient to effectively supervise students' competency development.

Ultimately, the intention to run these pilots was to experiment with newly designed online feedback and competency development tools as suitable instruments to facilitate students' competencies development and progress.

3.1 Research questions

Research on benefits of quality of feedback also with the support of digital self-assessment platforms abound in the literature. However, it is less known to what extent the quality of feedback could motivate and engage students in order to self-assess their own sketching skills. For the purpose of this study, we focus on the following research questions:

1. To what extent does the online *Competence Development Tool* enhance learning and motivate students to self-assess progress of sketching skills development?
2. What are students' perceptions about the self-assessment online *Competence Development Tool* as a suitable method to enhance competence development?

The assumption for this study was that the self-assessment online *Competence Development Tool* chart would make students aware of the multi-faceted nature and the various aspects involved in developing a competent level of sketching skills. We also assumed that it would stimulate students to frequently reflect about progress and monitor own development so that students would carry out the necessary

adjustments and improvements against achieving the ambitions on personal learning goals.

4 INSTRUCTIONAL DESIGN

Exploratory Sketching is a hands-on first year elective course at the department of Industrial Design. The course is taught every quarter and it is also open to students from the other engineering departments as well, for instance, Mechanical Engineering and Built Environment departments.

The learning outcomes of the *Exploratory Sketching* course aim at helping students develop sketching skills as a tool to explore, develop and communicate ideas and concepts. In the elective course *Exploratory Sketching* students develop their sketching skills compiling a number of sub-competencies such as fluency, accuracy, line quality, perspective and rendering techniques. The sub-competencies are first trained individually and later in a more integrated fashion. Furthermore, expert just-in-time feedback (by teachers) is also included in the course as a key in the successful training and development of the Industrial Design students' ability to critique and improve their own work.

The course consists of 5 ECTS (total 140 hours) and it is divided in 8 workshops of a total number of 16 hours, accompanied by 58 videos (13 hours) distributed along the 8 weeks-contact time course. In addition, this course relies on a strong self-study component which includes 111 hours. During the self-study component students complete weekly assignments wherein they apply insights and knowledge from the accompanying course content on Sketchdrive. The content is structured around a series of topics and themes aimed at building up the skill of sketching by training and integrating the individual sub-competencies in a controlled manner. These topics are *setting the mind, to draw is to see, linear products, cylindrical products, combined products, complex geometry, redesign and setting the scene*. With the last two topics students will start using the combination of all previously trained sub-competencies and acquired insights in the context of a creative design challenge. Furthermore, the self-study time opens up opportunities not only to work on assignments. It also enhances students to self-assess themselves by monitoring and evaluating own competences and reflect on achievements. In this course, Teacher Assistants (TAs) support the teacher with both logistic and content-wise activities.

4.1 E-learning approach for the *Exploratory Sketching* course design

The design of the *Exploratory Sketching* course has evolved in several stages. Starting out with a traditional on-campus lectures and workshops format the hands-on course was initially supplemented by a teacher blog and individual student blogs on Wordpress. This blended-learning set-up included as well the use of flip-the-classroom as an educational approach so that students would spend time in preparing course content during the self-study time before attending the lectures and workshops. In this regard, students would have more time for deep questions, peer interaction and hands-on assignments during contact hours where the teachers can also provide direct and qualitative feedback.

Additionally, students were requested to maintain an online portfolio on the Sketchdrive platform to document their work and progress. This new format facilitated

self-paced and collaborative learning, a-synchronous teacher feedback (Figure 1) as well as peer feedback on individual student work.

Figure 1. Example of teacher feedback on the Sketchdrive platform.

With the break-out of the COVID-19 pandemic worldwide and the Corona regulations at the TU/e university, teachers were involved in a rapid transformation process of education from on-campus to online and urgent remote type of education. The fact that the Exploratory Sketching course already had a blended-learning set-up allowed the teacher to swiftly transform the course into a fully online and remote format. Weekly workshops were now hosted remotely via a live video connection and used for group reflection, peer review, collective challenges and live feedback. By providing this elective (partially) online students were no longer bound by time and location and they are free to set their own pace and work on the course's assignments from anywhere. Additionally, a series of optional workshops were offered online when extra guidance was needed. This format potentially created opportunities to scale up student enrollment for this popular elective, made hands-on education available online, opened enrollment to other departments and reduced the need (and cost) to reserve physical facilities. To support the teacher in giving weekly personalized feedback on the students' work online two additional Teacher Assistants became essential.

With the lack of face-to-face interaction and the need for just-in-time feedback, additional online tools were added to the online set-up of this course in addition to the already existing online material developed in the blended-learning version of the course, the digital portfolios, assignments and online resource materials.

4.2 Competence Development Tool (CDT) chart

An online *Competence Development Tool* (CDT) chart was integrated in the course with the purpose of stimulating self-assessment students' development of sketching skills. The CDT consisted of nine criteria, i.e. confidence, accuracy, line quality, perspective, rendering, exploring, communicating, personal style, and shading) relevant for students to acquire and develop in the course (See Figure 2). The tool also includes 5 levels of expertise being 1 – Novice, 2- Advanced beginner, 3 – Competent, 4- Professional, and 5 – Master, against which students can score themselves. The students are asked in week 1 to make an estimation of the level of development or ambition expected to reach by the end of the course. In the example, the orange line shows the scored expected ambition of the student in week 1. The blue shading indicates the weekly growth in sketching competences. In addition, the CDT allows for additional creation of criteria in case students would like to challenge themselves with regards to other abilities. The purpose is to stimulate students to regularly assess the progress by themselves as well to encourage the possibility to adjust the learning curve to optimize the sketching skills.

Students fill out this chart at the start and the end of the elective to keep a record, set personal goals and reflect on the progress they make in learning. However, an online competence development tool becomes essential to foster self-directed learning and to help all staff and students structure the learning path at the ID department but also at other TU/e departments. With this tool a lecturer can create an overview of the (sub-) competencies involved and can monitor and guide the individual ambitions for each student.

5 METHODOLOGY

5.1 Research set-up and approach

The research has been carried out in two phasis including two different cohorts and four different groups.

Phase 1 – Research on the suitability of the *Competence Development Tool* chart to enhance self-assessment by visualizing the individual weekly development. This experiment was conducted with the students' cohort 2019/2020.

Phase 2 – The *Competence Development Tool* chart was again tested to research the impact of this tool on students' course performance. This experiment was carried out with students' cohort 2020/2021 in three different quartiles of the year. Slight changes were made to better explain the criteria and the different levels on the chart to ensure an optimal use of the tool in setting personal goals and documenting progress. We also switched to a bi-weekly schedule for recording the progress on the charts to make the progress more visible.

5.1.1 Participants

Students attending the *Exploratory Sketching* course in quartile 4 in academic year 2019/2020 and in quartile 3 in academic year 2020/2021 (See Table 1 and 2) took part in the quantitative as well as in the qualitative research.

Table 1. Quantitative research: Overview cohorts, students' comments collected and interviews

Students' cohorts	N= students attending the course	N= students' comments
Quartile 4 2019/2020	N= 52 students	N= 15
Quartile 1 2020/2021	N= 46 students	N= 5
Quartile 2 2020/2021	N = 50 students	N= 8
Quartile 3 2020/2021	N = 43 students	N= 5

Table 2. Qualitative research: overview students' cohorts and number students' interviews

Students' cohorts	Individual interviews
Quartile 4 2019/2020	N=7
Quartile 3 2020/2021	N=5

5.2 Research method

5.2.1 Quantitative research

During phase 1 of this study, a quantitative research was conducted. It consisted of the registration and analysis of the students' progress of the weekly competencies' development. The registration of parameters allowed for a weekly quantitative visualization of the level of achievement (See Figure 3 average of all students) against the ambitions that students stated at the beginning of the course. In addition, we also compared students' course performance in two quartiles, by analyzing the students' grades (Figures 4 and 5). The rationale was to understand whether there is a relation between attendance and students' grades. Finally, students' satisfaction was collected through the formal course evaluation filled in by the students as part of the quality assurance system of the department.

5.2.2 Qualitative research

Moreover, a qualitative study was carried out with limited number of students attending the *Exploratory Sketching* course. Comments from students from both cohorts quartile 4 in academic year 2019/2020 and students of quartile 1, 2 and 3 in academic year 2020/2021 were collected. In addition, in-depth interviews took place with a limited number of students to understand better the added values of the CDT chart.

5 RESULTS

In this section we present the results of the two research questions we formulated for this study.

RQ1 - To what extent does the online *Competence Development Tool* enhance learning and motivate students to self-assess progress of sketching skills development?

We collected the average of students' progress represented in the graph below (See Figure 3). In this graph the horizontal lines show the average of the students' ambitions regarding the nine sketching skills in different colors. The diagonal lines

indicate the average in growth in sketching skills development of the students participating in this study. The scale is based on a 10,000 (low) to 40,000 (high) values, and it is based on students' weekly self-evaluation. The values are collected every week to gain an overview on progress. As appreciated in the graph the lines including the skills steadily grow per week along the 10-week course. Despite the constant growth none of the skills achieve the average ambitions of the students of cohort 2019/2020. This result reveals that there is growth in competencies' development in all skills being Confidence and Perspective the most developed ones while Custom and Personal Style are the less developed ones. Reasons for that is that Confidence *"grows as you practice you get reinforcement and you become better in your competences..."*, says a student. Custom and Personal Style are less developed as *Personal Style is a skill you acquire along years and not only at once, and Custom is difficult to translate products in your personalized ones*, according to some students.

Figure 2. Competence Development Tool chart

Figure 3. Average students' growth in sketching competencies progress

In addition, we collected students' comments from two cohorts on the CDT. Comments are positive about the added value of the CDT *"Thanks to the competence chart, I was able to see my improvement and therefore gain more motivation to improve"*; *"After knowing the different competencies, I worked on them all very hard and I managed to hit most of my initial goals"*; *"I liked the competence chart as a means of visualizing your ambitions for different sketching skills. The chart also reminded me that you do not have to focus on every skill in every sketch. I developed most skills about as much as I would have liked during this course"*; *"By keeping my progress in the competence chart, I was able to see which competencies I had to improve in (perspective) and in which I was already quite good (e.g. communicating)"*. Also, taking a look to the percentage of the ambitions reached, we

can confirm that most of the students providing these comments reached between 60% to 100% their ambitions.

Moreover, we also interviewed students to find out how they have experienced the CDT chart. All students agree on the benefits of this tool as development becomes visual and insightful and helps reflect upon actions. For some students the tool helped “*looking at the skills from different angles. It provides a progression in perspective and help think critically about what still needs to be done to adjust to reach goals and ambitions*”, said students. Some students overestimated themselves and therefore, the CDT chart supported in realizing the gaps to bridge by getting a better understanding of how it grows throughout the weeks. Also, the fact that the tool allows for other additions to the criteria, helps look individually but holistically to the personalized development of the student. The tool, however, was considered to have some shortcomings as it was not clear what the scales represent and what the levels from beginner through professional or master really mean.

Regarding the influence of the self-assessment on sketching skills on quality of sketches or course achievement, we cannot draw a relation between the effect of the CDT and the quality of students’ sketches and sketching skills. We are however careful to make a relation between the attendance to the course sessions and the students’ grades being higher grades for students attending more sessions (See Figures 4 and 5). High attendance also correlated with a more intensive use of the CDT, but it is still unclear how these two factors influenced each other.

Figure 4. Attendance and grades Q2 2020/2021

Figure 5. Attendance and grades Q3 2020/2021

The teacher mentioned a positive effect according to the dashboard variables that allowed to monitor the overall progress and address students for improvement based on individual levels and progress. This made it possible to prioritize feedback on students that reported little progress by checking in on their portfolio on Sketchdrive first.

RQ2 – What are students’ perceptions about the self-assessment online *Competence Development Tool* a suitable method to enhance competence development?

We collected the students’ perceptions through the formal course’s evaluations. The quality assurance system of the department and at the whole TU/e consists of

evaluations that includes both open questions and Likert-scale 1 (low) to 5 (high) questionnaires. Students filled in the survey at the end of each course. As appreciate in Figure 6, students from different cohorts were positive the online methods used in this course. Students appreciated highly the feedback received from the teacher and from the tool as it helps reflect and adjust study behavior and evaluate quality of own work.

Figure 6. Students' perceptions on online methods used in this course

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study has been conducted to explore the effects of online tools that support students' self-assessment and stimulate the development of competences. Results of this study are positive and indicate the added value of the online *Competence Development Tool* chart. Students indicate that the CDT stimulates regular revision of own progress by self-assessing the development of the sketching competences. However, students pointed out that the CDT still needs to be adjusted as the scale degrees (i.e. beginner, competent, advanced, professional and master) and the description of what is expected from each competences are to be added to facilitate better understanding and use of the tool.

The results of this study add value to the body of knowledge regarding self-assessment and motivation for students to take actions regarding own progress. It shows commonalities with the insights of the research literature. As the findings in research, we argue that online feedback can be of great benefit to enhance students' development of competences, in this case, relevant to develop the sketching skills of future generations of Industrial Designers. Finally, this study sheds light on self-directed learning as a metacognitive skills crucial in engineering education that contributes to build the capacity of future engineers.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank the students attending the online course *Exploratory Sketching* of the department of Industrial Design for their participation and contribution to this pilot experiment. The feedback provided has served to make adjustments in the re-design of the course.

REFERENCES

- [1] Shen, R., Wang, M., Gao, W., Novak, D., and Tang, L. (2009). Mobile learning in a large blended computer science classroom: System function, pedagogies, and their impact on learning. *IEEE Transaction on Education*, Vol. 52, pp. 538–546.
- [2] Shih, R. (2011). Can web 2.0 technology assist college students in learning English writing? Integrating facebook and peer assessment with blended learning *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, Vol. 27, pp. 829–845.
- [3] Zhao, J., and Jiang, Y. (2010). Knowledge construction through discussion forum in a blended learning environment. In P. Tsang, K. S. Cheung, V. S. K. Lee, & R. Huang (Eds.), *Hybrid learning proceedings of the third international conference, ICHL2010*, pp. 395–406. Heidelberg: Springer.
- [4] Bagher, M., Marek, S. A., and Sibbald, A. (2007). Implementing web-assisted learning and engaging academic staff in the change process. *Journal of Organisational Transformation and Social Change*, Vol. 3, pp. 269–284.
- [5] Purvis, A. J., Aspden, L. J., Bannister, P. W., and Helm, P. A. (2011). Assessment strategies to support higher level learning in blended delivery. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, Vol. 48, pp. 91–100.
- [6] William, D. (2011). What is assessment for learning?, *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, Vol. 37, No. 1, pp 3-14, ISSN 0191-491X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2011.03.001>.
- [7] Hanrahan, S. J., and G. Isaacs. (2001). Assessing Self- and Peer-Assessment: The Students' Views. *Higher Education Research and Development*, Vol. 20. pp. 53–70. doi:10.1080/07294360123776
- [8] Nicol, D., and Milligan, C. (2006). Rethinking Technology-Supported Assessment Practices in Relation to the Seven Principles of Good Feedback Practice. In *Innovative Assessment in Higher Education*, edited by C. Bryan and K. Clegg, pp. 64–77. London: Routledge.
- [9] Hattie, J., and Timperley H. The Power of Feedback. (2007). *Review of Educational Research*. Vol. 77, No. 1, pp.81-112. doi:[10.3102/003465430298487](https://doi.org/10.3102/003465430298487)
- [10] Peat, M., and Franklin, S. (2002). Supporting student learning. The use of computer-based formative assessment modules. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, Vol. 33, No.5, pp. 515–523. doi:10.1111/1467- 8535.00288.
- [11] Taras, M. (2003). To feedback or not to feedback in student self-assessment. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, Vol. 28, No. 5, pp. 549–565. doi:10.1080/02602930301678.
- [12] Zimmerman, B. (1995). Self-regulation involves more than metacognition: A social cognitive perspective. *Educational Psychologist*, Vol. 30, No.4, pp. 217–221. doi:10.1207/s15326985ep3004_8.